

Proposal stage KPIs	WP responsible	M12 update
Objective 1 - Partner with user communities to create a toolkit for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows that allow life-scientists to benefit from open science practices in the emerging European federated data landscape.		
Established partnerships with user communities that capture experiences and embed these in good practices for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows	WP2	<p>Progress by M12:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engaged with the five core ELIXIR Communities and 12 other Communities to provide entries on software best practices and infrastructure use; feedback obtained from 16 Communities in total so far - F2F joint meeting with WP3 involving Community representatives took place in Padova, October 2024 <p>Plan to M24:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - short talks from ELIXIR Nodes on their software quality activities will take place during WP2 monthly meetings starting February 2025 - Five selected core Communities (3D-Bioinfo, IDP, Single Cell Omics, Systems Biology, Biodiversity) will be engaged in the M2.3 workshop "ELIXIR-STEERS WP2 workshop on research software management quality indicators" to take place in June during AHM in Thessaloniki. The workshop aims to be a hands-on session with the selected Communities to work together on best practices recommendations and research software quality indicators
A toolkit developed consisting of guidelines, best practices and services that supports software development and recognition of individuals involved in software development (WP2, WP3)	WP2, WP3	<p>Progress by M12:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strategy for inclusion of credit for research assets decided, which will form the basis for the recommended recognition framework part of the best-practices compendium. - Collection of SMP-related best practices resources (aligned with WP2), to feed the Knowledge Model used for the implementation of SMP in DSW. <p>Plan to M24:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improvement of SMPs with feedback collected and input from topic-specific workshops
Community-wide agreement on key indicators for technical, scientific, and environmental benchmarking (WP2) embedded into established software and workflow benchmarking systems (WP3)	WP2, WP3	<p>Progress by M12:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing efficiency and green indicators within WP3, to be implemented in OpenEBench for the technical benchmarking <p>Plan to M24:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use cases from communities defined for testing the implementation in OpenEBench, including the key efficiency indicators
Practices for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows (WP2, WP3) are adopted and embedded in ELIXIR Nodes (WP4), supporting the European federated data landscape and Horizon Europe projects	WP2, WP3, WP4	<p>Progress by M12:</p> <p>WP4 - The course outline for the new carbon footprint module has been drafted, including green computing. We implemented a survey about the syllabus, requesting feedback from WP2, WP3, and all project members. Based on the results of this survey and the discussions held during the WP4 annual meeting, the course outline for the new module was drafted. EATRIS was contacted for collaboration on the environmental sustainability topic</p> <p>Contacts were also developed with the EMBL's sustainability team. In SPARKLE we designed and selected meaningful KPIs for an overall impact framework that could serve the basis for other Nodes to start or upgrade their impact assessment efforts.</p> <p>Plan to M24:</p> <p>WP4 - The content of the carbon footprint module will be developed following the Training Platform guidelines and the ELITMa processes for module development. Expertise to develop the module content will be identified within STEERS members at first.</p>
Demonstration of the greening potential and reduced carbon footprint of software best practice by applying toolkit and indicators in community-driven activities (WP2)	WP2	<p>Progress by M12:</p> <p>Completed key milestones, including the Community Engagement Scoreboard (M2.1) and the Collection of Best Practices and Indicators for Research Software (M2.2), which provides a landscape analysis of existing solutions and categorization of best practices within ELIXIR and beyond. These efforts lay the foundation for developing actionable guidelines to enhance research software quality, sustainability, and impact.</p> <p>Plan to M24:</p> <p>First outputs expected to be presented</p>
Stimulate engagement and uptake by users via European and national communication and outreach programmes (WP5)	WP5	<p>Progress by M12: No update, task starts on completion of toolkit</p> <p>Plan to M24: Prepare communications and engagement plan</p>

Objective 2 - Enable the landscape for cross-border data analysis in the life sciences by embedding common practice across the whole European Research Area via effective national ELIXIR Nodes.		
Build a common toolkit to enhance the operational and managerial capacity of ELIXIR Nodes that comprise all aspects of sustainability (operational excellence, business planning, interactions with industry and impact assessment) (WP4, WP5)	WP4, WP5	<p>Progress by M12: WP4 - The basic Node Mapping features exercise was preliminary defined. The scope of the ELIXIR Node Handbook is being actively refined.</p> <p>Plan to M24: WP4 - Information from the COG yearly survey will be added to the basic Node Mapping exercise for all nodes (including non participant nodes) and targeted interviews with current nodes</p>
Expand ELIXIR's Membership by transitioning candidate countries into fully operational national Nodes using capacity building actions (WP4, WP5)	WP4, WP5	<p>Progress by M12: - Austria joined ELIXIR as Observer (ADD DATES) and Technical University of Vienna is about to become Beneficiary in STEERS - Romania joined ELIXIR as Observer (ADD DATES) and RSB is about to become a Beneficiary in STEERS as partner (ADD DATES) - Croatia still has same status in ELIXIR as a prospective Member, but has beneficiary in STEERS - Malta on track to join ELIXIR as Member (ELIXIR Board approved application in Nov 2024). University of Valetta will become Beneficiary in STEERS in future</p> <p>WP4 - New candidate countries have been attending the WP4 meetings.</p> <p>Plan to M24: WP4 - The new countries will go through an onboarding process (support of WP1 and coordination of the project) to actively participate in the tasks activities.</p>
Strengthen excellence in RI management with an ELIXIR training programme that complements established Europe-wide offerings with the infrastructure specific needs (WP4)	WP4	<p>Progress by M12: This KPI was planned for years 2 and 3.</p> <p>Plan to M24: The Carbon Footprint module content will be developed. A face-to-face edition of the ELITMa Module Governance & organisation is planned, co-located with the Node Triangle meeting in March in Lisbon (PeoplePulse CoS project). All the existing ELITMa modules will be made available to STEERS members.</p>
Strengthen the capacity of national training programmes (WP4) to scale the dissemination, training, and uptake of the ELIXIR software development toolkit for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows	WP4	<p>Progress by M12: Members from WP4 have attended the WP2 and WP3 meetings to ensure that the training plans will include green software development.</p> <p>Plan to M24: Workshops with WP2 and WP3 will be organised with the aim to identify topics and teaching skills required for a software development. A survey will be deployed, which will include the topics identified in the workshop with WP2 and WP3. A "programme of courses" will be drafted based on identified needs and confirm that with WP2 and WP3 members.</p>
Work with funders to embed the practice in data and software management plans in guidelines to grantees (WP5)	WP5	<p>Progress by M12: - No update</p> <p>Plan to M24: - Majority of work to follow after STEERS recommendations are developed and as part of policy event planned for Summer 2025. Planned Policy Brief will also address this point</p>
Objective 3 - Partner in Europe and internationally for global competitiveness and sustainability		

Development of national SME and industry partnerships to support the European innovation ecosystem (WP5)	WP5	<p>Progress by M12:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 15 companies (large and small size enterprises) have been interviewed regarding their usage of open source workflows and software through big industrial conferences like BioTechX, Festival of Genomics, and previous ELIXIR network (https://docs.google.com/document/d/1tT9t756Lq9GZHkF4buyQt5XYQF7zAWVrBmnpEoUWKKM/edit?tab=t.0). - Four Industry and Innovation Focus Groups meetings have taken place over the 12 months on the following topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Training for industrial audience - Enhancing SME Access to European Research and Technology Infrastructures through the European Commission - Pitching exercise to companies - Achievements and challenges in industry engagement <p>Plan to M24:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A report regarding the usage of open source workflows and software - A workshop on the same topic as the report - Four more Industry and Innovation Focus Groups meetings to collect good practices of industry engagement activities per Node
Partnerships with other ESFRI RIs to strengthen the wider RI landscape (WP5) and support adoption of robust, reproducible, and green workflows across RI facilities.	WP5	<p>Progress by M12:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A Memorandum of Agreement was signed with INSTRUCT-ERIC and the renewal of the MoU with Euro Bioimaging is finalised. - A pilot exercise to map collaborations between ELIXIR and other ESFRI RIs was launched with few selected Nodes to gather feedback previous to ELIXIR-wide roll out in early Q2 2025. <p>Plan to M24:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Roll out of ESFRI RIs collaboration mapping will take place. - Explore possibility to formalise a MoU with DiSSCo ESFRI RI.
Foster global knowledge-exchange to drive good international practices and embed international partnerships in Node activities (WP5)	WP5	<p>Progress by M12:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First draft for review of the revamped International Strategy. <p>Plan to M24:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Updated International Strategy to be published in Q2 2025. - Seek to formalise a collaboration agreement with GBIF. - Engage and support Nodes in international activities, especially with Latin America and Africa.
Deliver a Node dissemination and communications toolkit that enables ELIXIR Nodes to amplify engagement with scientists and other stakeholders (WP5)	WP5	<p>Progress by M12:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> First draft of updates to ELIXIR Communications Strategy and Branding Guidelines, as a prerequisite for Node Comms Strategy toolkit <p>Plan to M24:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ELIXIR Comms Strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feb 25 to Jan 26 - Node feedback, release and awareness raising, implementation Node Comms Strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • March to April 25 – gather requirements, outline draft • May 25 – write draft • June to Aug 25 – Node feedback and final draft • Sept 25 – Milestone due • Oct 25 to Jan 26 – release, awareness raising, support with implementation